

Voluntourism Stakeholder Analysis

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Introduction

Voluntourism is the evolution of what started as volunteering trips for humanitarian aid, combining recent years' urge for meaningful vacations by experiencing something different; standing out of the crowd. Voluntourism is a progressively popular form of travel that the research community is not indifferent to (Guttentag, 2009). According to McLennan and Banks (2019, p. 338), "*voluntourism is the phenomenon that fuses the altruistic practice of international volunteering with the hedonistic thrills of the tourism industry, and it has been widely critiqued for commodifying development and reinforcing thin forms of neoliberal global citizenship*". To understand the importance and structure of voluntourism, as well as its global scale, both in the developing and the developed countries, it is essential to identify the major stakeholders. The purpose of this paper is to propose a formalized research approach. By synthesizing the diverse roles identified in the literature into a stakeholder matrix, we provide a tool for analyzing the structural variables and power dynamics that define the industry.

This analysis is in two stages, which are linked. The first stage analyzes the most common stakeholders found in the existing literature and addresses the impact of the stakeholders on the implementation of voluntourism programs as well as the impact of this form of travelling on each stakeholder. Utilizing the findings of the content analysis, the authors develop a stakeholder matrix that categorizes each group according to their roles, responsibilities, and organizational types. The second stage involves a relational analysis, visualized through a stakeholder map. This mapping exercise moves beyond static categorization to illustrate the dynamic interdependencies and power flows between actors. By documenting these connections, the research highlights how the interactions between international intermediaries and local facilitators shape the operational realities of the voluntourism landscape.

The contribution of this analysis lies in identifying the key stakeholder variables that define the global image of voluntourism, thereby providing a structural basis to evaluate emerging trends and suggest future research directions. This approach defines the roles of the stakeholders while it helps the understanding of the connections between stakeholders and the significance of those connections. Findings from the research thus indicate that voluntourism is increasingly being implemented within developed countries (Tsartas et al., 2020; VolunteerWorld, 2023; Vrasti and Montsion, 2014) challenging the dominant view that these activities are mostly implemented in developing countries. Examining these stakeholders explores the complex relationship between voluntourism, development, and social justice. Specifically, it illustrates how the market-driven interests of private agencies (neoliberalization) may overlap or conflict with the civic motivations of volunteers. An other important aspect noteworthy is the integration of UNSDGs on the purpose of the programs (Baillie Smith and Laurie, 2011).

Literature Review

The theoretical foundation of voluntourism was largely established by Wearing (2001), who framed the practice as a pathway for personal development and a de commodified alternative to mass tourism. However, the discourse has since evolved through more critical lenses. Butcher (2003) and Vrsti (2013) argue that voluntourism often functions as a vehicle for neoliberalism, where aid is marketized and the volunteer becomes a consumer of poverty. This is further complicated by what Mostafanezhad (2014) terms the 'sentimental economy' of voluntourism, where the global image of the sector is shaped more by the emotional experiences of the tourist than the material needs of the host.

Voluntourism is particularly prevalent among young adults during the 'Gap Year,' a transitional period typically occurring after secondary education, during university, or upon graduation. During this interval, individuals often pause their formal education to travel or engage in work, seeking practical experience and personal clarity before committing to specific career paths (Simpson, 2004). This experience is frequently included in professional curricula vitae, regardless of its direct relevance to the individual's specific field of study (McGloin and Georgeou, 2015). The proliferation of social media and the increasing desire for experiential travel among youth have significantly contributed to the popularity of these programs. Simultaneously, universities, recognizing the value of international experience and community service, actively support student participation in such initiatives (Hammersley et al., 2018). In some instances, these activities are integrated into formal internships and apprenticeships, frequently supported by institutional funding. Beyond the youth demographic, a distinct category of voluntourists includes retirees from developed nations. The mobilization of this group is often driven by Western governmental policies that seek to reintegrate retirees into the global labor market, utilizing the expertise and 'inactive' human capital of an aging yet economically capable population (Hansen and Slagsvold, 2020).

In addition to the research objectives, this paper highlights specific areas of concern that contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the proposed stakeholder framework. Voluntourism has been on a steady growth course the last decade and has established itself as an innovative form of travel (McLennan, 2014). The relatively recent existence of voluntourism programs in developed countries in addition to developing countries, the emergence of platforms and agencies focusing on this subject is proof that there is fertile ground for further growth (Hammersley et al., 2018). With the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in mind, voluntourism programs promise additionally to being a form of sustainable and alternative tourism, participants to contribute the achievement of the goals set by the United Nations. Popular voluntourism platforms like VolunteerWorld or GoOverseas are openly supporting and integrate these goals into the choices of the facilitators and programs they run (Schech, 2017; Schneller and Coburn, 2018). Each program is usually accompanied by the marking of the goal or goals from the SDGs concerned (Go Overseas, 2023; GoAbroad, 2023; VolunteerWorld, 2023).

Methodology

The methodology employed is qualitative content analysis utilized for the purpose of the stakeholder mapping. By synthesizing existing literature on voluntourism, the authors identify and categorize key stakeholders based on their roles, responsibilities

and influence. This categorization results in a stakeholder analysis matrix, which functions as a conceptual framework for understanding the diverse variables within the sector. Subsequently, the study conducts a deeper analysis of the interdependencies and power dynamics between these actors. This is visualized through a stakeholder relations map, illustrating the flow of resources and influence across the global voluntourism network. Ultimately, this matrix serves as a methodological tool designed to systematize the identification and analysis of variables in future empirical research.

Identifying Voluntourism Stakeholders

In order to systematize our understanding of voluntourism and its implementation, it is necessary to identify the stakeholders involved and the relationships that define their interactions. The primary stakeholders identified across contemporary literature include voluntourists, local communities, facilitators, voluntourism agencies, voluntourism platforms, and local businesses. Additionally, while less frequently discussed, mass tourism businesses represent a structurally significant stakeholder of the sector (McLennan, 2019; Schneller and Coburn, 2018).

The following sections categorize these stakeholders by synthesizing their roles and responsibilities into a structured matrix. This categorization highlights the spectrum of actors through which voluntourism is produced and consumed. By mapping these roles, the analysis transitions from a descriptive list to a relational framework, emphasizing how the interdependencies between local and international actors drive the global voluntourism landscape

Volunteer Tourists or Voluntourists

The primary stakeholders to analyze are the voluntourists. Within the existing literature voluntourist is the standard term for these participants, and it will be utilized through this paper. While early research often focused on altruism (Wearing, 2001), contemporary studies highlight a core demographic originating from the Global North, predominantly from North America, Europe and Australia (Hernandez-Maskivker et al., 2018). The age of participants typically ranges between 18 and 45 years with the average age being 26, though participation among retirees is also documented (Hansen and Slagsvold, 2020).

Voluntourists generally self-fund their experience, covering airfare and travel insurance while paying fees to the facilitating organization for accommodation, airport transfer to the accommodation, administration, support and orientation (Jakubiak, 2020; Lyons, 2003). Participants are usually expected to provide labor three to six hours per day, five days per week, leaving substantial time to socialize, engage within the local community and participate in traditional tourist activities (Broad, 2003). Consequently, voluntourists function as both service providers and consumers. Personal growth remains a primary motive for participation, as individuals seek to develop their personal identities and global perspectives (Schech, 2017).

Literature further distinguishes voluntourists on their primary focus: the "volunteer-minded" and the "vacation-minded" (Coghlan and Gooch, 2011). "Volunteer-minded" individuals prioritize the mission and labor aspects of the trip, whereas "vacation-minded" participants emphasize leisure, socialization, and touristic attractions dedicating a smaller portion of their time to volunteering (Coren and Gray, 2012). This

distinction is central to understanding the varying impacts these actors have to communities.

Facilitators

Responsibility for the implementation of voluntourism programs on a local level rests with entities that typically hold the status of an NGO (van Zyl et al., 2015). Through the stakeholder analysis process, it was observed that this key stakeholder can take various forms. To provide conceptual clarity this paper introduces the term "Facilitator". This designation is intended to assist future research as existing literature often uses inconsistent terminology such as "operators" or "local partners" making it challenging to establish links between relevant studies.

It is vital to understand the role facilitators play in managing various factors required for successful program implementation. They are tasked to maintaining a balance that mutually benefits both the host community and the voluntourists (Hamzah, 2014). In current literature the distinction between Facilitators, Voluntourism Agencies and Voluntourism Platforms is frequently overlooked (Schech, 2017).

Facilitators are responsible for identifying the needs of the host community, securing appropriate placements, and managing logistics such as accommodation and recreational activities (van Zyl et al., 2015). To recruit participants, they utilize websites and social media to promote the uniqueness of the experience, often validating their programs through testimonials and visual media (van Zyl et al., 2015). Furthermore, Facilitators ensure that voluntourists contribute effectively to their placements while adhering to the cultural norms of the host community (Devereux, 2008). Part of their mandate includes preparing the host community for the arrival of voluntourists. It is common for Facilitators to provide recruited voluntourists with orientation sessions to ensure a safe and smooth coexistence (Hammersley, 2013; McMorran, 2017).

Voluntourism Agencies

As the demand for experiential travel grew exponentially, new actors emerged within the voluntourism sector. These entities, frequently identified in the literature as "sending organizations" or "parent organizations" function as Voluntourism Agencies (McLennan, 2019; Schech, 2017).

In some instances, local Facilitators that achieved operational resilience and scale, have undergone vertical integration, transitioning into the role of a voluntourism agency (Lupoli et al., 2015). The operational framework of these organizations closely mirrors that of traditional travel; consequently, conventional tourist agencies have also begun establishing partnerships with local facilitators aiming to get involved in this alternative form of tourism (McLennan, 2014).

To increase their visibility to potential participants, local facilitators often establish cooperations with these agencies. Voluntourism agencies specialize in market promotion, participant recruitment, and the strategic acquisition of new local partnerships to broaden their service portfolios (Hammersley, 2013). It is common for agencies to select an exclusive partner within a specific geographical region and conduct an on-site quality assessment before officially adding a program to their list of offerings. At this point it is worth mentioning that these agencies often prioritize sales

metrics and participant satisfaction over the actual socio-economic impact on the local community or the facilitators capacity to manage volunteer influxes (Schneider, 2018).

Beyond marketing, a key responsibility of these agencies, is the management of the online footprint which involves the curated display of testimonials and the mitigation of negative feedback. While voluntourists often pay significant fees for travel arrangements, insurance and administrative support, the local facilitators usually receive only a percentage of these total costs. (McLennan, 2019).

Voluntourism Platforms

The digital landscape has fundamentally altered how individuals identify and access meaningful travel opportunities, with social media and specialized web aggregators serving as primary search tools (van Zyl et al., 2015). Voluntourism Platforms have emerged as a distinct stakeholder group, functioning as digital marketplaces rather than traditional sending agencies. Prominent examples include “VolunteerWorld” and “Go Overseas”, which were often founded by former voluntourists to address the need for centralized databases that allow users to compare diverse global programs (Go Overseas, 2023; VolunteerWorld, 2023). On these platforms facilitators can upload their available programs accompanied by attractive descriptions and photos containing snapshots of community work and local landscapes to attract potential participants (van Zyl et al., 2015). Unlike Agencies, which often handle full travel logistics, Platforms primarily provide the infrastructure for transparency and comparison.

To maintain institutional credibility, these platforms implement quality assurance protocols based on legal frameworks and internal standards. Evaluation is typically conducted through on-site inspection or the verification of a Facilitator’s organizational documentation. A defining feature of these platforms is the integration of user-generated content, specifically peer-to-peer ratings and testimonials. Voluntourists who have completed a placement can provide verified reviews, which serve as a powerful marketing tool (Go Overseas, 2023; GoAbroad, 2023; VolunteerWorld, 2023). Both Agencies and Platforms leverage these testimonials to foster expectations of a “unique and guilt-free experience,” a narrative that is central to the modern voluntourism market (van Zyl et al., 2015).

Local Community

The local community is the most significant, yet often most vulnerable, stakeholder in voluntourism. Traditionally, research has focused on host communities within the developing world. This landscape has evolved. As the need for environmental, social or humanitarian support exists globally, voluntourism programs are increasingly implemented in developed nations, such as Greece and Italy (Messmore and Davis, 2020; Tsartas et al., 2020). This shift highlights that host communities are defined by a specific localized need rather than a country’s economic status (Omoto et al., 2012).

A community qualifies as a voluntourism destination when there is a clear requirement for support that complements, rather than substitutes for local labor (Jakubiak, 2016). Many of these communities are initially non-touristic as participants in such programs often seek authentic cultural experiences that have not been altered by mass tourism. For a partnership to succeed, there must be mutual respect and clear communication between the community and the facilitator (Messmore and Davis, 2020).

The participation of a local community in such programs can serve as a catalyst for broader development (Kontogeorgopoulos, 2014). In some instances, the presence of voluntourism allows locals to organize resources and utilize their cultural heritage to transition into a more established tourist destination (Hamzah, 2014). However, achieving a sustainable balance requires proper information and engagement of the local community, particularly the institutions that host voluntourists, as well as clear and accurate information for interested potential voluntourists, accompanied by appropriate training and orientation prior to the start of their program.

Local Businesses

Local businesses' reaction towards voluntourists differ depending the region, country and local culture (Kontogeorgopoulos, 2014). At this point it is pertinent to stress that research on the coexistence of voluntourists and local businesses is scarce. There are cases where local businesses benefited from voluntourism and cases where they have treated voluntourists as an obstacle (Hamzah, 2014).

As voluntourism programs are typically found in areas where some form of crisis or need exists (humanitarian, environmental, economic, etc.), the proper handling of voluntourists by local businesses can be a factor of development or moderation of the problem (Hammersley et al., 2018). There have been cases where the majority of local businessmen are against voluntourism, as found in the literature, in communities where there have been particularly sensitive issues such as a refugee crisis (Tsartas et al., 2020). In other cases, the local community embraced voluntourists with examples of locals benefiting of voluntourism and operate commercially aligned with these programs (Aquino and Andereck, 2018). There are also instances in which voluntourists, by promoting their experiences on social media, have contributed to positioning these locations as tourist destinations (Hernandez-Maskivker et al., 2018).

Mass Tourism Businesses

While mass tourism businesses are often peripheral to the volunteer mission, they are identified in the literature as structurally significant stakeholders that ensure the sector's resilience by providing the transport and hospitality infrastructure required for international travel (Guttentag, 2009). As voluntourism destinations mature, these businesses become 'collateral stakeholders' that facilitate the scaling of programs through established logistical networks (Kontogeorgopoulos, 2014).

The inclusion of these actors in the Stakeholder Analysis Matrix (Table 1) highlights the "tourism" dimension of the voluntourism product. For example, the cooperation between facilitators and local tourism businesses to develop "free-time packages" for participants confirms that the experience is marketed and consumed as a leisure-labor hybrid. By documenting these connections, this research provides a structural framework that characterizes voluntourism as an alternative tourism product, rather than a purely humanitarian endeavor. This perspective aligns with critical literature (Butcher, 2003; Vrasti, 2013) that views the sector through the lens of marketized development.

The following Voluntourism Stakeholder Analysis Matrix (Table 1) synthesizes the findings from the content analysis. The stakeholders are categorized by their specific roles, responsibilities, and organizational types, as identified within the literature. This matrix serves as the structural foundation for the subsequent relational mapping,

allowing for a systematic comparison of how international and local stakeholders interact within the voluntourism supply chain.

Table 1: Voluntourism Stakeholder Analysis Matrix

Identification				
Stakeholder	Role	Responsibilities	Type	References
Voluntourism Agencies	Voluntourists suppliers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Find facilitators for cooperation -Financial and sustainability background check of cooperating facilitator - History and impact check of cooperating facilitators - Check cooperating facilitators to meet the Agency's operational standards - Check cooperating facilitator's programs - Check cooperating facilitator's local community impact - Set rules, activity agreement, code of conduct and Terms and Conditions for all cooperations with cooperating facilitator - Publish available programs - Retrieve voluntourists - Receive payments from voluntourists - Responsible for the payment of the local facilitator - May arrange travel insurance - May organize plane tickets - Organize voluntourism programs (more than one destination, VIP packages etc.) 	International Organization	Baillie Smith and Laurie, 2011; Devereux, 2008; Griffiths, 2016; Hammersley, 2013; Lupoli et al., 2015; McLennan, 2014, 2019; Schech, 2017; Schneider, 2018
Voluntourism Platforms	Voluntourists suppliers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cooperating facilitators' background check and quality control - Set rules for facilitators to register - Set rules for voluntourists to register - Set communication rules between voluntourists and facilitators - Receive commission by volunteers or/and by facilitators - Use a review promotion system for volunteer programs and/or organizations 	International Organization	Aquino and Andereck, 2018; Go Overseas, 2023; GoAbroad, 2023; Sujarittanonta, 2014; van Zyl et al., 2015; VolunteerWorld, 2023

<p style="text-align: center;">Facilitators</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Voluntourism Implementation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Responsible for volunteer programs - Running the volunteer programs - Register to platforms and Voluntourism Agencies to recruit voluntourists - Find hosting place for voluntourists - Onsite Support for voluntourists - Responsible to orientate the voluntourists - Create/find volunteer programs - Introduce international voluntourists to the local community - Receive payments from voluntourists or platforms or agencies - Measure the impact of the activities to the local community and the voluntourists 	<p style="text-align: center;">Local Organization</p> <p>Butcher, 2003; Devereux, 2008; Hammersley, 2013; Hamzah, 2014; Hernandez-Maskivker et al., 2018; Jakubiak, 2020; McMorrان, 2017; Mostafanezhad, 2014; Rozakou, 2012; Schech, 2017; Tsartas et al., 2020; van Zyl et al., 2015; Vrasti, 2013; Wearing, 2001</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Voluntourists</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Customers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Responsible to carry out the pre-assigned activities - Represent themselves, their country and the hosting organization in the local community - Responsible for the payment of the program they have selected - Write a review or testimony on the online volunteering platforms after finishing their program 	<p style="text-align: center;">International Individuals</p> <p>Bright Founder, 2015; Broad, 2003; Butcher, 2003; Cousins and Sadler, 2009; Devereux, 2008; Doidge et al., 2020; Germann Molz, 2016; Griffiths, 2016; Guiney, 2018; Hammersley, 2013; Hansen and Slagsvold, 2020; Jakubiak, 2020, 2012; Kontogeorgopoulos, 2014; Lyons, 2003; McLennan, 2014; McMorrان, 2017; Millerman, 2016; Mostafanezhad, 2014; Schneider, 2018; Vrasti, 2013; Wearing, 2001</p>

Local Community	Communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Respect the other cultures - Recognition of the need for voluntourists - Coordination between voluntourists and locals - Accept international voluntourists to blend with the local community 	Local individuals	<p>Aquino and Andereck, 2018; Baines and Hardill, 2008; Broad, 2003; Butcher, 2003; Coghlan and Gooch, 2011; Coren and Gray, 2012; Hammersley et al., 2018; Hamzah, 2014; Heu, n.d.; Kontogeorgopoulos, 2014; Levinson, 2020; Lupoli et al., 2015; Madziva and Chinouya, 2016; Mostafanezhad, 2014; Palacios, 2010; Spalding, 2013; Vrasti, 2013; Wearing, 2001</p>
Local businesses	Collateral Interest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Respect the other cultures - Recognition of the need for voluntourists - Coordination between voluntourists and locals - Treat international voluntourists with respect - Introduce the international voluntourists to the local community 	Local businesses	<p>McLennan, 2019; Messmore and Davis, 2020; Omoto et al., 2012; Woosnam and Lee, 2011</p>
Mass Tourism businesses	Collateral Interest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Respect the other cultures - Recognition of the need for voluntourists - Coordination between voluntourists and locals - Treat international voluntourists with respect - Introduce the international voluntourists to the local community - Cooperation with facilitators for the developing of free time packages for international voluntourists 	Local tourism businesses	<p>(Guttentag, 2009; Kontogeorgopoulos, 2014; McLennan, 2019)</p>

Stakeholders Relations Analysis Mapping

In the existing literature, authors argue about the good practices of voluntourism and its impact on local level (Guttentag, 2009; Kinsbergen et al., 2021). Nevertheless, it is empirically evident in various cases that such programs have positive impact on local communities and voluntourists (Hernandez-Maskivker et al., 2018). Cooperation between stakeholders is inextricably linked to the impact and the results of such programs.

The initial gap for the existence of a voluntourism program in a region is first identified by a local team (local group, NGO, CSO, individuals, etc.) (Hamzah, 2014). Following, the local team, having identified the priorities of the action area, assumes the role of the Facilitator. This stakeholder has the responsibility for the implementation, evaluation and dissemination of the results (Devereux, 2008). To attract voluntourists the facilitator must advertise available programs primarily through social media. Another important role of the facilitator is the sufficient training and briefing of both voluntourists and the local community about all the aspects of the programs before implementation. At the same time, facilitators have the role of the intermediary for the resolution of occurring issues that may arise in order to sustain the smooth coexistence of all actors (van Zyl et al., 2015).

From the side of a local community, although receiving aid might initially seem appealing, when it comes to the implementation of the programs the locals' reaction is mixed or skeptical (Baines and Hardill, 2008). Evidently, the effective assistance of the local community by voluntourists is a prerequisite for the existence of these programs. Moreover, there are cases where the activity from voluntourism became the trigger for development in areas of need where local residents capitalized on the arrival of voluntourists (McLennan, 2019). The main stakeholders that should be accounted for the smooth implementation of such a program are the facilitators (Kontogeorgopoulos, 2014).

Local businesses in areas where voluntourism programs exist, usually benefit from the participants in such activities, as the behavior of voluntourists outside of voluntary work is similar to that of a responsible tourist (Messmore and Davis, 2020). On the contrary this is not always the case with mass tourism businesses (Broad, 2003). For instance, since accommodation is typically provided by the facilitator, collaboration with mass tourism businesses such as hotels and restaurants is less frequent.

Facilitators' ability to reach out to individuals interested in voluntourism is limited and this is where the Voluntourism Agencies intervene. The agencies will find facilitators or vice versa, where they already run or are able to run programs and they are assured consistent volunteer flows (Baillie Smith and Laurie, 2011). Agencies are likely to take on some of the facilitators' responsibilities such as the communication and preparation of voluntourists before departure.

In addition, Voluntourism Platforms, despite having only recently emerged as stakeholders, enable facilitators to create a personal account on their platform and post their available programs along with their description. At the same time the platforms can also be used by agencies to promote their programs. These platforms give voluntourists the ability to compare programs and choose the best match for them (Sujarittanonta, 2014).

From the existing literature it appears that as more international stakeholders are involved “controlling” the facilitators (voluntourism agencies, voluntourism platforms), local stakeholders (facilitators, local community, local businesses, mass tourism businesses) become more affected and marginalized (Coren and Gray, 2012). On “Figure 1” is presented the Voluntourism stakeholders Relations Analysis Map. Local stakeholders are represented with green color while international with blue. Voluntourists, since they are on site and their presence is temporary while at the same time their actions influence the locals, are represented with grey.

Figure 1: Voluntourism Stakeholder Map

Scientific Contribution

The scientific contribution of this paper lies in the systematic categorization of key stakeholders providing a structural framework to better understand the global voluntourism landscape. By synthesizing diverse roles into a unified stakeholder analysis matrix, this research identifies the core variables that define the field, offering a foundation for future empirical studies.

Furthermore, this analysis documents the interdependent relationships between local and international actors, visualizing these flows of influence through a stakeholder relations map. By introducing the term “Facilitator”, the paper offers conceptual clarity to an area of the literature often characterized by inconsistent terminology. Ultimately, this research serves as a methodological approach to help scholars examine how voluntourism functions as a development tool or as a crisis response mechanism across both developing and developed nations.

Conclusion

In the existing literature stakeholders in voluntourism are frequently identified in a fragmented manner, with researchers often focusing on specific actors rather than a collective ecosystem. This research provides a systematic foundation by synthesizing previous documentation to offer the academic community a comprehensive record of key stakeholders. The introduction of the term "Facilitator" represents a crucial contribution, as it acknowledges a vital stakeholder that assumes various forms and has previously been difficult to isolate in the literature. Furthermore, by analyzing stakeholder relations through visual mapping, this study provides a clear reference point for future research into the complex forces and interdependencies within the sector.

A significant observation of this paper is that while the majority of the existing research approaches voluntourism from a humanitarian-social perspective, this study, by mapping the systematic involvement of commercial intermediaries, structurally verifies that voluntourism operates as an alternative tourism product within the global market. The resulting matrix clarifies the synergies, cooperations, and interdependencies that exist between actors, highlighting that each stakeholder occupies a specific position in voluntourism with defined, albeit often informal, limits.

By distinguishing frequently conflated roles such as "Voluntourism Agencies", "Voluntourism Platforms" and "Facilitators", this paper provides the conceptual clarity necessary for more rigorous sectoral analysis. While information on newer stakeholders such as "Voluntourism Platforms" remains limited due to their recent emergence, their growing footprint is evident. Ultimately, this research addresses the lack of integrated data on stakeholder roles, providing a framework that can be parameterized across varying scopes of voluntourism globally.

Research Limitations

During the research it was observed that there are several potential gaps that require further analysis in the existing literature of voluntourism. Information about some stakeholders is limited and, in some cases, their online presence was used to explore their roles.

Another issue presented, which stems from the fact that so far research on voluntourism is done from a humanitarian-sociological point of view, is that literature is limited concerning voluntourism programs hosted in the Global North. Whilst, with a simple search in the existing available Voluntourism Platforms and Voluntourism Agencies we can find a plethora of programs in European countries, Australia, etc.

Future Research

Further empirical investigation should be directed toward stakeholders for whom data remains scarce in the current literature, as well as the evolving geography of the sector as developed nations increasingly become destinations for voluntourism action. There is also significant scope for introspective analysis regarding pricing structures and the distribution of fees within voluntourism programs. One frequently documented area of malpractice is the misrepresentation of programs by agencies or facilitators, alongside substandard orientation sessions that fail to prepare participants effectively (Guttentag, 2009). Future studies should also examine the mechanisms through which local

communities and businesses are informed and engaged. As implementation strategies appear to vary based on the facilitator's management choices and the sensitivity of the project, current conclusions remain largely hypothetical. Consequently, the methodological framework provided in this research can serve as a basis for follow-up studies concerning specific branches of voluntourism. This includes further analysis of the power dynamics between stakeholders and the development of best practices for program implementation. Finally, a critical gap remains in the literature regarding the long-term perceptions and reactions of host communities toward these interventions.

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